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PHYSICAL THERAPY ROLE IN GAIT TREATMENT FOR CP DIAPLEGIC
PATIENT

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Introduction

Cerebral Palsy (C.P.) is a condition when the brain is damaged or paralyzed before birth, during birth or within 24 months after birth. The part of the brain that controls movement and posture is damaged, therefore children with C.P. have difficulty in sitting, standing, walking or taking care of their Activities of Daily Living (ADL) ¹. Cerebral Palsy can be classified by the type of movement disorder it causes ². CP Diplegia constitutes 60-70 % of the spastic CP population which defined with both legs affected and upper body usually normal or very mildly affected ^{1,3}. Diplegic children have normal mental function and can communicate without difficulty. Their oromotor and gastrointestinal functions are normal. They often have visual perceptual deficits and strabismus. There is a tendency to fall backwards because of poorly developed balance reactions ³. The main problem in spastic Diplegia is walking difficulty. Balance disturbance, muscle weakness, spasticity and deformities result in abnormal gait patterns typical for Diplegic children ^{3,4}. Abnormal gait increases energy consumption causing fatigue. Most Diplegic children start cruising at two years of age and walk by age four. Neuromotor function improves until age seven. Children who cannot walk by then in spite of appropriate treatment usually become limited walkers. Among all types of CP Diplegic children benefit most from treatment procedures. Unlike hemiplegic children they cannot reach their potential if left untreated. With treatment they may become productive members of the society. Every effort is worth spending when treating a Diplegic child ³.

As a child grows, the bones and muscles have to grow, but muscles don't grow unless they're stretched. Growth plates in bones are programmed to make bones longer, but the shape of the bones depends on the forces acting upon them. If the force on a bone is normal, the bone takes a normal shape. If it's abnormal, the bone

remodels into a deformed position. Children with cerebral palsy have poor motor control, poor balance and spastic muscles that resist stretching. They can't exercise enough to stretch their muscles. As their bones grow, they drop into a crouch. The muscles in the front of their legs become too long; those in the back become too short⁴.

The objective of this study is to make a good understanding for the main gait problem for the Diaplegic patient and what causes it so that and depend on the overall review we are gone select our main treatment to reach our patient concern.

Normal Gait

When pain, paralysis or tissue damage occurs, abnormal gait is the result. Loss of motor control will also result in a gait disorder. When physical therapies are confronted with pathological gait they must have sound knowledge of the characteristics of normal gait so that they can accurately detect and interpret deviations from the normal gait pattern. However, it is important to keep in mind that each individual displays certain variations from the norm which are superimposed on the normal pattern of walking.

There are two major abilities essential to walking. The first, equilibrium, is the ability to assume an upright posture and maintain balance. Locomotion, the ability to initiate and maintain rhythmic stepping, is the second. However, although these two abilities are essential, there are many additional contributing factors involved. The musculoskeletal system must provide intact bones and well functioning joints as well as adequate muscle strength. Normal muscle tone is very important and is controlled at the subcortical level. Muscle tone must be high enough to resist

gravity, but low enough to allow movement. Reciprocal innervations of muscles allows for graded action between agonist and antagonist necessary for skilled movements. Vision is also vital to normal walking. It is particularly important when other sensory input is reduced. Vision gives information about the movement of the head and body relative to the surroundings and is important for the automatic balance responses to changes in surface conditions. Other sensory systems that are important are the vestibular, auditory, and sensorimotor systems.

Normal gait requires the proper functioning of the musculoskeletal system and the nervous system. The nervous system is responsible for both motor output and sensory input. The basic divisions of the gait cycle are stance and swing. The entire period during which the foot is on the ground is the stance phase. The swing phase begins when the foot is lifted from the floor until the heel is placed down. While walking the thorax rotates in clockwise and counterclockwise directions opposite the pelvic rotations. Some people display more rotation of the thorax, while others display more rotation of the pelvis.

With each step the pelvis drops a few degrees on the side of the non-weight bearing, or swinging, leg. While the leg is swinging, the hip abductors of the weight bearing leg contract in order to prevent the pelvis from falling excessively on the unsupported side. If the abductor muscles are paralyzed the result is Trendelenburg gait in which the pelvis falls on the unsupported side. The degree of lateral pelvic tilt varies greatly with the individual, particularly in females. The walking base, or side to side distance between the two feet, is usually 2-4 inches. The toes normally point laterally 5°-10°.

In humans there is more than one group of muscles responsible for propulsion. As a result it is possible for one to compensate for a defect. For example, when walking across slippery ice there is a transfer from pushing against the ground to lifting the leg up. Although locomotion is still possible using alternative muscle groups, stride length and velocity are often reduced as a result.

The gait cycle, consisting of stance and swing, can be further broken down into eight sub-phases.

Phase 1: Initial Contact

The moment when the red foot just touches the floor. Normally, the heel is the first part of the foot to touch the ground. The hip is flexed, the knee is extended, and the ankle is dorsiflexed to neutral. Meanwhile, the blue leg is at the end of terminal stance.

Phase 2: Loading Response

The double stance period beginning when the foot contacts the floor and continuing until the other foot is lifted for swing. Body weight is transferred onto the red leg. Phase 2 is important for shock absorption, weight-bearing, and forward progression. The blue leg is in the pre-swing phase.

The next task of the gait cycle is single limb support during which one limb must support the entire body weight and provide truncal stability while progression must be continued.

Phase 3: Mid Stance

The first half of the single limb support interval. It begins with the lifting of the blue foot and continues until body weight is aligned over the supporting foot. The red leg advances over the red foot by ankle dorsiflexion while the hip and knee extend. The blue leg is advancing in its mid-swing phase.

Phase 4: Terminal Stance

Begins when the red heel rises and continues until the heel of the blue foot hits the ground. Body weight progresses beyond the red foot as increased hip extension puts the leg in a more trailing position.

Phase 5: Pre-Swing

The second double stance interval in the gait cycle. It begins with the initial contact of the blue foot and ends with red toe-off. Ground contact by the blue leg causes the red leg to increase ankle plantar flexion, increase knee flexion, and decrease hip extension. Transfer of body weight from ipsilateral to opposite limb takes place.

Phase 6: Initial Swing

Begins when the foot is lifted from the floor and ends when the swinging foot is opposite the stance foot. The red leg is advanced by increased hip flexion and increased knee flexion. The ankle only partially dorsiflexes to ensure ground clearance. It is

during this phase that a foot drop gait is most apparent. The blue leg is in mid-stance.

Phase 7: Mid Swing

Continues from the end point of the initial swing and continues until the swinging limb is in front of the body and the tibia is vertical. Advancement of the red leg is accomplished by further hip flexion. The knee is allowed to extend in response to gravity while the ankle continues dorsiflexion to neutral. The blue leg is in late mid-stance.

Phase 8: Terminal Swing

Begins when the tibia is vertical and ends when the foot touches the floor. Limb advancement is completed by knee extension. The hip maintains its flexion and the ankle remains dorsiflexed to neutral.

Throughout the course of a gait cycle three tasks must be accomplished.

Weight acceptance, the most demanding task in the gait cycle, involves the transfer of

body weight onto a limb that has just finished swinging forward and has an unstable alignment. Shock absorption and the maintenance of a forward progression are also important components of this phase. The next task of the gait cycle is single limb support during which one limb must support the entire body weight and provide truncal stability while progression must be continued. The final task of the gait cycle is limb advancement, which requires foot clearance from the floor. The limb swings through three positions as it travels to its destination in front of the body.

The neural control of gait (i.e. how the nervous system organizes and controls the activation of skeletal muscle and maintains balance) is very complex and not completely understood at this time. It involves complex sensory, motor, and central nervous systems. The effectors include muscles, tendons, ligaments, and skeletal structure. It has been shown that the basic gait rhythm does not require input from the periphery. The spinal cord itself is capable of generating near-normal gait movements, but is not able to provide stability, support body weight, or propagate the body forward. An example of such neural activity is seen when a baby is held upright with its feet just touching the floor. The baby will start moving its legs as if stepping, but is unable to balance or support itself independently. The cerebellum and brainstem must be left intact in order to provide increased inter- and intra-limb coordination, support of body weight, and active propagation.

While walking the body center of mass is outside the base of support 80% of the time. There are two methods for controlling the dynamic equilibrium of the body: reactive and proactive. Reactive control of stability is used for unpredictable upsets to balance, and therefore depends on sensory input. Proactive control is broken down into two subtypes. The first is involved in counteracting perturbations caused by the

gait movements themselves. The second is an experience-based system that uses vision to predict potential causes of dysequilibrium and implements appropriate avoidance strategies.⁵

Abnormal Gait

Muscle imbalance, spasticity and deformities at the hips, knees and ankles contribute to the specific posture and gait patterns typical for Diplegic CP³.

Types of abnormal gait pattern in spastic Diplegic patient:

1) Scissoring

In spastic Diplegia a common gait abnormality is scissors gait or crossing over which is a tendency to walk with the hip flexed and adducted^{3,6}. Scissoring is frontal plane pathology. It occurs as a result of hip adductor and/or medial hamstring spasticity³. the trunk leans forward, the knees are bent and the feet are held in equines. The lack of free rotation at the hip makes it necessary to swivel the trunk from side to side as each leg swings through. The narrow walking base (due to hip adduction) and the tendency to fall forward (due to hip and knee flexion and equines) are often dealt with by using crutches. Correction of these deformities is therefore an important objective⁶.

2) Jump gait

The jump gait pattern is very commonly seen in children with diplegia, who have more proximal involvement,

with spasticity of the hamstrings and hip flexors in addition to calf spasticity⁷. Jump gait is defined as excessive hip flexion, knee flexion and equinus in stance. The cause is lower extremity flexor muscle spasticity. The child walks with hips and knees in flexion and ankles in plantar flexion looking like an athlete getting ready to jump.³

3) Crouch gait

Crouch gait is the second most common sagittal plane pathology and it occurs in the older diplegic³. It is defined as excessive dorsiflexion or calcaneus at the ankle in combination with excessive flexion at the knee and hip⁷. Common causes of crouch gait are short or spastic hamstrings, hip flexor tightness and excessive ankle dorsiflexion which is the last one may result from isolated triceps surae lengthening without

addressing the spastic hamstrings. Hamstring tightness causes crouch and a short step length when walking. When sitting, tight hamstrings pull the ischial tuberosities and tilt the pelvis posteriorly causing kyphosis and sacral sitting³.

4) Toe-walker

In some children, the Achilles tendon is tight and restricts dorsiflexion of the ankle so that the child walks on tiptoe and cannot stand with the heel flat.

The feet and ankles appear normal at first glance and the parents may already have been reassured that 'there is nothing wrong' by the time they reach an orthopedic clinic. On careful examination, dorsiflexion of the ankle is restricted or absent, the child cannot squat with the heels to the ground and stands with a characteristic

forward stoop. If they attempt to stand upright, the children fall over backwards. The signs are worse when the child is barefoot.

Untreated, the Achilles tendon will usually stretch enough to acquire a reasonable gait but the patient will usually have a 'bouncing' gait because they have to rise on tiptoe when the body's weight passes in front of the foot.⁸

Complications related to spastic Diplegic gait pattern:

1) stiff knee

stiff knee is a sagittal plane pathology characterized by limited range of motion in the knee joint, especially a lack of flexion in swing. It occurs because of spasticity of rectus femoris muscle or unopposed rectus femoris function after hamstring lengthening.

Compensatory movements of hip external rotation and circumduction are observed. The patient experiences difficulty going up steps. Step length is shortened, foot clearance is poor, and shoes wear out rapidly.

2) Genu recurvatum

Genu recurvatum occurs in the stance phase of walking and is generally associated with mild equinus caused by triceps surae spasticity, excessive spasticity in the quadriceps, and may be related to weakness of the hamstring muscles or contracture of the hip flexors.

3) Torsional deformities

Femoral anteversion is naturally increased in all babies and regresses as the child grows. Persistent femoral anteversion causes scissoring and in toeing gait. Adductor and flexor tightness also contribute to scissoring caused by increased femoral internal rotation. The knee and ankle joints do not function on the plane of movement and walking difficulty is increased.

4) Pes valgus

Pes valgus is characterized by abnormal eversion of the heel, convexity of the medial border of the foot and prominence of the head of the talus. It occurs because of spasticity of the peroneals, extensor digitorum communis and triceps surae. External tibial torsion creates a valgus stress at the ankle and contributes to pes valgus .

The natural history of certain mild developmental problems of the lower extremities such as pes planovalgus and genu recurvatum is benign. These disorders are seen in able bodied children as well and disappear spontaneously around 7-8 years of age as ligaments get tighter.

Severe pes valgus deformity causes callosities on the medial side of the foot, midfoot abduction and hallux valgus.

5) Hallux valgus

Hallux valgus occurs secondary to pes valgus or pes equinovalgus in ambulatory children. Correct equinovalgus deformity

first, hallux valgus deformity improves after this. Spasticity of the adductor hallucis muscle causes hallux valgus in plantigrade feet³.

Neuromedical Interventions

1) Muscle Relaxants

Oral medications have been used for children with cerebral palsy who have spasticity, for the dampening of excessive motor activity. Black et al. indicated that there are different types of motor control problems that result from brain injury. They fall into the following categories: spasticity, 60%; dyskinesia, 20 %; ataxia, 1%; and about 20% have a combination of the preceding with one of the movement disorders being dominant. Pranzatelli labels the movement disorders slightly differently as dystonia, hyperkinesias choreoathetosis, and myoclonus. Commonly used oral muscle relaxant drugs include diazepam, dantrolene, and baclofen. There has been little study of the functional effects of these drugs in children, and little is known about optimal dosing, safety, and side effects. McManus adds tizanidine and clonidine to this list and indicates that the sedating effects of these oral drugs are not well tolerated in children. In particular, Black et al. list baclofen as a drug to be used with caution, and the physician's Desk Reference does not recommend its use for cerebral palsy or for children under the age of 12 years.⁹

2) Neuromuscular Blocks

Infants and children with CP have difficulty balancing the agonist against the antagonist muscle group for smooth, coordinated, efficient motor function. Instead, they frequently overuse one muscle, the agonist, and have great difficulty activating its antagonist, which may cause muscle shortening, contractures, eventually deformity. According to Sutherland et al., a dynamic deformity results from

dominance of certain agonist muscles over antagonist muscles. This muscles imbalance results in abnormal motion function. Dynamic deformity will frequently become fixed over time. The goal is to manage a dynamic deformity carefully to delay the need for surgical intervention, which is often required with fixed deformity.

A dynamic deformity offers options to the child, family, and team. Sutherland says that the ideal treatment must:

1. Prevent fixed deformity
2. Be painless
3. Be cost effective and
4. Not result in any serious complications

It is well known that children with cerebral palsy have spasticity that presents itself in typical patterns for specific type of CP but in its own unique way in each child. This spasticity can interfere with function in multiple arenas including motor skills, self-care, communication, and fine motor activities. One method of reducing spasticity in certain muscles is to do neuromuscular blocks.

Since 1993, botulinum toxin (Botox) A injections have been used to treat children with cerebral palsy with spasticity the interferes with their function. It is an injection into the dominant agonist muscle at the nerve terminals to cause temporary paralysis of the muscle lasting 3 to 6 months. Botulinum A toxin blocks the release of Ach by the synaptic vesicles. Recovery occurs by terminal sprouting of the nerves. Because axonal innervation of the neuromuscular junction is eventually re-established, multiple sessions are usually required. The sessions need to be separated

by at least 12 weeks to decrease the risk of developing neutralizing antibodies. It has fewer clinical complications, is easy to use, is more pain free, can be administered without sedation, and diffuses readily into the muscle; however, it is high cost with possible short-term effects.

According to pidcock, the clinical goals for treating a child with Botox A include the following:

1. Improve function
2. Prevent or treat musculoskeletal complications
3. Increase comfort
4. Facilitate ease of care
5. Improve appearance

The use of injections must be in combination with a therapeutic program of stretching, bracing, and functional exercise to ultimately assist the child's functional improvements to his or her maximal level of function. Studies of the use of Botox A have shown improvements in children with cerebral palsy, such as delay of orthopedic surgery, improvement in gait variables, achievement of independent ambulation, improvement in the functional performance in standing and walking, and a decrease in spasticity. Currently, medical teams are pairing Botox A injections with a period of serial casting to the limb for various lengths of time. This combination may prevent deformities, thereby potentially avoiding orthopedic surgeries later in life, and may achieve the ROM goals in less time than with casting alone and prevent the

subsequent decrease in ambulation status that sometimes happens with surgical release of the gastrocnemius.

O'Neil et al. studied the changes in the provision of PT services to the children who received Botox A injections and agreed that changes are made at the impairment level as well as the functional level skills. However, she proposed that the Botox A injections are actually an adjunct to the PT services and not the reverse, which is commonly accepted. She stated that the injections enable the therapist to provide more impairment and functional level strategies so that goals and outcomes are more successful. Her study helps to identify strategies useful in achieving the goals and improving outcomes. Fragala et al. studied children's achievements after Botox A injections based on their level of function according to the GMFCS and found that the children who had higher functional levels at baseline (level (I) and level (III)) and had injections in one muscle group verse multiple groups made improvements in disability and the satisfaction level was higher.⁹

So relaxing the spastic muscles with botulinum toxin injections may aid the treatment team to visualize how the child will function when his spastic muscles are surgically lengthened. However, the toxin cannot show its real effect in some older children with already shortened muscles.

Botulinum toxin may be combined with surgery in the older child. Inject muscles which have mild spasticity and no shortening with Botulinum toxin and surgically lengthen the severely spastic short muscles. This combination approach adopted in the recent years enables a swifter return of function, less complications and less muscle weakness because of less extensive orthopedic surgery.³

Neurologic & Orthopedic surgery

Most deformities of Diplegic can be prevented or corrected with appropriate surgery. Therefore the most successful outcomes are seen in Diplegic children. Delay surgery until the child is able to cruise holding onto furniture or walk holding hands. Provide intensive physiotherapy and botulinum toxin injections to lengthen the spastic muscles and prevent contractures during this period. The ideal age of operation is between 5-7 years. Early surgery is necessary in cases with hip instability, knee flexion contracture because of spastic hamstrings and contracture of gastrocnemius-soleus unresponsive to physiotherapy, botulinum toxin or serial casting.³

Neurological intervention

1) Selective Dorsal Rhizotomy (SDR)

Selective dorsal rhizotomy (SDR), otherwise known as selective posterior rhizotomy (SPR), is not a new surgical approach to the treatment of children with CP but has been a poorly understood procedure aimed at reducing the spasticity of children with CP. Oppenheim et al. have provided a current explanation for the effectiveness of this intervention simplified that removing the spasticity does not, however, produce improved motor control. The team approach is absolutely vital to this procedure, both before and after surgery. Patient selection is critical to a good outcome as only two types of patients are appropriate candidates. The first group includes patients who are functionally limited by spasticity but who have sufficient underlying voluntary power to maintain and eventually improve their functional abilities. Keen intelligence and motivation are also helpful. The second group includes nonambulatory patients whose spasticity interferes with sitting, bathing, positioning, perineal care, classroom activities, and so on. The surgery is typically completed across segments L2 to S2 or L2 to S1 and only a selected number of dorsal

rootlets are sacrificed – those that appear to have the retest influence on the spasticity and produce abnormal movement patterns.

Research from the 1990s has shown that patient who have undergone SPR have been very positive about the outcome and that the quality of life has been enhanced. This surgical intervention had delayed orthopedic surgery by improving both passive and dynamic ROM in children, specifically in the hip adductors, hamstrings, and heel cords, and preventing lateral migration of the femoral head .

Research published in 2004 indicates that there are longer term sequel in 2004 indicates that there are longer term sequel that must be considered when determining whether a child is a good candidate for SDR. Of significance is the increase in spinal deformity at long-term follow-up consisting of lumbar hyperlordosis (50%), grade I spondylolisthesis (18%), and scoliosis (24%). A positive change in the child's functional statuses after SDR is inconclusive at this time. Evidence suggests that hip adductor spasticity is reduced and that strength may or may not be decreased in these same muscles, while the ambulatory statuses of the children may or may not change, especially when compared to a population of children with spastic Diplegic CP who received only intensive PT services. This is again in direct conflict with the findings published in the 1990s.

In light of the inconclusive evidence on the functional changes after spinal dorsal rhizotomy, it is imperative that the medical team look very closely at all candidates for this neurosurgical procedure and compared the potential outcomes and child and family desired outcomes to other forms of intervention.^{9,10}

2) Intrathecal Baclofen Pump

Another method of managing spasticity in the child with CP is by insertion of an intrathecal baclofen pump (IBP). Baclofen has been used orally for over a decade

in the management of spasticity. As noted previously, however, there are potential drawbacks making it less likely to be used with children with CP. The effectiveness of oral baclofen is limited by its inability to cross into the central nervous system. Doctors are now able to implant a pump into the abdomen of an older (and somewhat larger) child with CP and insert a catheter directly into the intrathecal space. Concentrations of baclofen have been found to be 10 times higher in the CSF with the intrathecal pump than when using oral baclofen and to have a gradient from the lumbar spine to the cervical region of four to one. McManus indicated that the effectiveness of this method is as good as a rhizotomy but may be preferable as it is not ablative and reversible. The criteria used for patient selection includes a client with moderately severe spasticity of spinal and cerebral origin as can be found in some cases with CP, trauma, anoxic brain injury, stroke, or dystopia.

The other requirement includes the following:

1. The client must have sufficient body mass to maintain the pump
2. The patient and the family must understand and accept the cosmesis of the pump
3. There must be appropriate goals of the client, family, and team
4. The family and team must be committed to the necessary follow-up
5. Patients must be free of infection and medically stable

Clients with minimal or moderate functional limitation are not candidates for insertion of the IBP. Once the client has been chosen with the entire medical team and family, he or she must go through a trial of baclofen injected into the intrathecal space during a hospitalization prior to implanting the pump. This is done with 50, 75, or 100 µg of baclofen, during which time the client must be monitored very closely and under strict protocols.

The three most common goals stated for choosing the baclofen pump are to decrease pain/improve comfort, prevent worsening of deformity or function, and improve ease of care. Gooch et al. reviewed multiple studies of clients who have received the pump. Findings included a significant reduction in tone, improvement in function, reported improved upper extremity function, caregivers report of increase ease of care, and improvement in gait in a few.

It should be noted that the amount of baclofen may need to be altered according to the results noted by the client and caregiver and that the pump must be refilled once every 1 to 3 months depending on the size of the reservoir and the amount of baclofen utilized. Some clients have experienced too great a reduction in their tone, which resulted in losing function as they achieved their prior function through use of their stiffness and spasticity.

The role of the PT is to help to identify clients appropriate for the baclofen pump, assist in the evaluation process to distinguish between spasticity that interferes with function and that which the client uses to function, document change with the trial of baclofen and the change after implantation, assist in setting realistic outcomes, and while in the hospital, assist the family and client to become acquainted with bodies that feel and move differently from pre surgery. Postoperatively, the PT plays a key role in assessing equipment needs, rehabilitation service need, and documentation of outcomes as well as strengthening, improving motor control, and monitoring skin integrity. Note all clients will require therapy services. Those with desired outcomes of increased ease of care and decreased pain will not likely need much intervention. The client whose desired outcomes include functional changes will need intervention, the frequency of which the PT can help to determine, but the client

may need to wait about a month before therapy services begin. Safety is of paramount importance as all functions will "feel" different to the client initially. ^{9,11}

Orthopedic Surgery

Most deformities of diplegics can be prevented or corrected with appropriate surgery. Therefore the most successful outcomes are seen in diplegic children. Delay surgery until the child is able to cruise holding onto furniture or walk holding hands. Provide intensive physiotherapy and botulinum toxin injections to lengthen the spastic muscles and prevent contractures during this period. The ideal age of operation is between 5-7 years. Early surgery is necessary in cases with hip instability, knee flexion contracture because of spastic hamstrings and contracture of gastrocnemius-soleus unresponsive to physiotherapy, botulinum toxin or serial casting.³

1)The Hip

a) Subluxation / Dislocation

Dislocated hips are a more serious problem for the child, as the hip(s) may become painful, sitting may become more difficult, decubitus ulcers may be caused by asymmetric weight bearing, care of the child may be made more difficult, and fractures are possible. With progression of the subluxation, surgery may become necessary, in which case tenotomies or myotomies are the treatment of choice. The effectiveness of muscle transfer is controversial. ⁹

b) Adduction Tightness

Indications for management of the hip adductors are:

- 1) Prevention of hip subluxation
- 2) Improvement in a scissore gait

3) Improvement care of the perineum

When the migratory percentage is 25% to 60% in CP hip disease and the child is between the ages of 2 and 8 years, it is necessary to perform surgical lengthening according to Miller. Soft tissue release tends to be ineffective when the child is older as there is too much bony deformity. The hip adductors can be lengthened in isolation or the iliopsoas can be lengthened as well, dependent on the presentation of the child.^{9,12}

c) Flexion Tightness

Surgical intervention involves lengthening of the iliopsoas muscle. It is rarely done in isolation but rather as one part of multiple surgical sites in a child with greater functional limitations.^{9,13}

d) Internal Rotation Deformity

Femoral anteversion, rather than muscular action, is a consistent deformity associated with exaggerated internal rotation during gait. Anteversion interferes with functional ambulation by tripping the child when the toe of one shoe gets caught behind the heel of the opposite shoe. A femoral derotation osteotomy, which may include medial hamstring release, is the standard surgery performed for this deformity. Miller indicates that a pri-ilial pelvic osteotomy is almost always done with femoral varus and shortening osteotomy to correct posterior-superior acetabular dysplasia.⁹

2) The Knee

Knee flexion deformity is often related to spastic, shortened hamstrings and may be secondary to a hip flexion contracture. Persistent flexion of the knee can lead to a contracture of the knee joint capsule and shortening of the sciatic nerve.

Indications for surgical lengthening of the hamstrings include:

- a. Kyphotic seating due to shortened hamstrings
- b. Fixed knee flexion contractures
- c. Popliteal angle of greater than 40 to 45 degrees or straight leg raise less than 45 degrees
- d. Knee flexion of 20 to 30 degree at foot contact during gait
- e. Knee flexion during midstance of 20 to 30 degrees

Variation on lengthening of the hamstrings have been developed, with the medial transfer of the distal rectus femoris tendon to the sartorius or gracilis being the more successful. In extreme cases of harmful spasticity, selective neurotomies have been performed on the hamstring branches of the sciatic trunk. Posterior capsulotomy is indicated when there is a fixed knee flexion contracture of 10 to 30 degree and is done in conjunction with a hamstring lengthening.^{9,13,14}

Root's goals of distal hamstring lengthening include the following:

- a. Eliminate or diminish inefficient crouch gait pattern
- b. Improve stride length
- c. Decrease compensatory ankle equinus and hip flexion

- d. Minimize internal rotation in gait
- e. Improve sitting balance and posture
- f. Decrease abnormal pull that can cause hip dislocation⁹

3) The Ankle and Foot

a. Equinus Deformity

Equinus, a very common foot deformity in children with CP, results from a muscular imbalance between the plantar flexors and dorsiflexors. It can be manifested as toe walking in the ambulatory child, as premature heel rise during gait, or as premature ankle plantar flexion moment during gait. Children with more severe involvement may have difficulty with foot placement on the pedal of the wheelchair, assisted stand-pivot transfers, and donning of shoes. Achilles tendon lengthening (both the gastrocnemius and the soleus are lengthened) is the most frequent surgical intervention for equinus deformity^{9,15}.

Rosenthal and Simon have had success with young children as well and indicate that if the procedure is done at 6 years of age or younger, a repeat procedure can be anticipated in 6 to 7 years. In the younger patient, the recurrence rate is 14%; in children older than 6 years of age, the recurrence rate drops to 1%. Overlengthening is the most common complication of surgery, and it results in calcaneal gait or an increase in dorsiflexion during stance. This gait is crouched in nature, with increased energy demands and subsequent shortening of the muscles in the hips and knees.⁹

b. Pes Valgus

Pes valgus is a deformity that includes eversion, plantar flexion, and inversion of the calcaneus with abduction of the forefoot. These positions cause a medial prominence of the talus, which is commonly accompanied by callous formation on the skin. The deformity is usually flexible and can be corrected by reducing the subtalar joint and forefoot to a neutral position with the ankle plantar flexed. Three situations contribute to the deformity:

- a. Spastic peroneals muscles that change the axis of rotation of the subtalar joint to a more horizontal alignment and abduct the midfoot and forefoot
- b. Gastrocnemius/soleus contracture causing plantar flexion of the calcaneus
- c. Persistent fetal medial deviation of the neck of the talus⁹

Surgery is indicated when conservative measures not possible . the foot deformity can be of highly varied severity and therefore require different approach in surgery. The most common of the later procedures that are performed include:

- a. Grice extra-articular subtalar arthrodesis
 - b. Triple arthrodesis for rigid deformities
 - c. Gric-Schede procedure⁹
- c. Varus Deformity

Varus deformity is less common in children with CP and seen mostly in the population with hemiplegia and Diplegia. It results from imbalance between weak peroneals muscle and spastic posterior or anterior tibialis muscles.

It is best to delay surgery until about 8 years of age and manage the foot with positioning, splinting, stretching, and strengthening until that time. The indication for surgery is a foot that is in varus in stance phase of gait or during swing phase of gait. The varus foot is very unstable and it is easy to acquire a strain or sprain on it.

A variety of surgical procedures are performed for this deformity, including lengthening or splitting and transferring of either the posterior or anterior tibialis muscles.⁹

4) Multilevel surgery

Multilevel surgery is performing multiple surgical interventions at a single session. The problem of evaluating the efficacy of multi-level surgery is complex¹⁶. This concept evolved when physicians realized that doing one operation at a time did not address the complex gait pathologies of CP. Perform all surgery directed at the hip, knee and ankle such as hip adductor releases, hamstring and gastrocnemius lengthenings or rectus transfers simultaneously during a single session to correct jump, crouch, stiff knee or scissoring gait. Add bony procedures for deformities such as hip subluxation, femoral anteversion, external and internal tibial torsion and severe pes valgus. Prescribe intensive physiotherapy to strengthen the muscles, prevent contractures and increase function after multilevel surgery. All children do not need multilevel surgery. Some have mild problems and require lengthening of one or two muscles only. Tailorize treatment according to the child's needs.³

Physical Therapy Examination

Physical Therapy examination of a child with movement problem has two basic purposes. First, physical therapy examination accompanying a detailed history enables an accurate diagnosis. Second, it allows the treating therapist to define the impairments and disabilities, determine the functional prognosis and set treatment goals in children with CP. These then help devise a treatment plan for each child. A detailed history and physical therapy examination help select the right treatment and prevent expensive and extensive work-up.

Physical therapy examination of the child with CP is not easy. It is a three-way relationship between the child, the therapist and the family. Adjustment problems can cause fear, distrust, confusion, and anxiety in the family and in the child. This disturbs their capability to understand the problem and cooperate with the treatment team. The therapist must be willing to deal with anxious, confused, frustrated and unhappy families and frightened children. The examination cannot succeed unless the therapist gains the parents' confidence and trust. Parents will trust a therapist who takes a genuine interest in their child.

1) History

History is a key component in evaluating the child. It provides valuable information for diagnosis. In children with a definite diagnosis, the timing of achievement of developmental milestones and the presence of associated impairments help to decide a functional prognosis. The therapist gains insight into the parents' expectations and disappointments from previous treatment procedures. Knowledge of previous botulinum toxin injections, physiotherapy, surgical procedures, outcomes,

complications, and psychological burden are key issues when making a treatment plan.

History taking provides the time and room to build a sense of understanding between the family and the therapist. The goal is to make the child and the family comfortable so that the clinical examination will be accurate.

2) Clinical Examination

Observing the child's movements is the initial and a crucial part of the examination. Observe before you touch. Perform a neurological, musculoskeletal and functional examination, although not necessarily in that order. Every therapist develops his or her own style and sequence of examination over the years.

3) Neurological Assessment

Neurological evaluation of the infant and the child requires adequate knowledge of neurological developmental stages.

a) Mental status

Observe the child's orientation and interest in the surroundings. Watch for eye contact, following objects, alertness, and ability to obey simple commands.

b) Vision and hearing

The diagnosis of visual and hearing loss in infants can be easy. Call the child when he is not looking. Clap your hands or deliberately drop an object to make a noise behind the child and watch the response.

c) Reflexes

Evaluate the persistence of primitive reflexes and the absence of advanced postural reactions. The presence of primitive reflexes beyond 6 months of age is a sign of poor prognosis.³

4) Assessment of Movement

Much of the information about an infant or child's movement and posture can be gathered by observing the child when he or she enters the treatment area. The infant and child can also be observed while taking a history and discussing with the parents the various concerns that have brought them to a rehabilitation or rehabilitation program.

Observation of the baby or young child being held in the arms or lap of the parent or caregiver can reveal important information. The following questions may be answered through observation:

1. How does the mother hold me baby? Does she support the head and trunk, or does she hold the baby at the pelvis?
2. Are the baby's head and trunk rotated or collapsed consistently to one side?
3. Do the baby's arms come forward to hold the mother or play with a toy in midline? Are the arms held behind the body with the scapulae adducted, or are the arms flexed and adducted against the trunk?
4. While being held, does the baby thrust backward into trunk extension or collapse forward into trunk flexion?
5. How are the lower extremities held: Are they adducted tightly in extension or are they floppy in flexion and abduction?
6. Is there isolated movement at the toes or ankles, or are the ankles held in plantar flexion or dorsiflexion? Is the foot everted or inverted, and are the toes held loosely or tightly curled?

This type of observational analysis is not limited to the child held in the parent's arms. When the child comes at the physical therapist in a wheelchair,

there are additional questions that may add to the baseline information.

1. Did the child independently propel the wheelchair, or did someone help him or her?
2. In addition to mobility, does the wheelchair provide total postural support for major segments of the body? If the segments are free of support from the wheelchair, are those segments of the body in good postural alignment and do they move freely?
3. Does the child tend to thrust backward in the chair into trunk extension? Is the pelvis positioned in a posterior or an anterior tilt? If the child does posture him- or herself in this manner, is there similar thrusting and tightness in the extremities?
4. Is the child seated in a reasonably symmetric position or are there significant asymmetries in the posture
5. Does the child seem comfortable in the chair?

Children with less severe movement disorders may ambulate into the department. The following group of questions will be helpful in assessing the quality of movement of the ambulatory child.

1. Did the child ambulate with or without an assistive device, such as a walker, cane, or crutches?
2. Did the child need physical assistance from another person while ambulating?
3. Is the child's gait pattern stable, and is the child safe?
4. When assessing spatial and temporal parameters such as length of step, stance time, swing time, or base of support, is the gait pattern generally symmetric or

asymmetric?

5. Does the child's trunk collapse into lateral flexion on weight bearing on one or both legs, or is the trunk maintained in proper antigravity extension?
6. Does the child have a heel-toe gait pattern? Does the Child stands on the balls of the feet?
7. Are the hips and knees locked or stuck in extension during stance phase, or are they falling into gravity or pulled into flexion with the child in a crouched position?

In addition to the gross observational assessment Described, the therapist should examine individual aspects of motor function as part of the overall evaluation of the child. The therapist should begin with the level of function appropriate to the child's age and functional ability. The following list of positions provides a guideline by which to assess functional anti gravity control: Supine, Prone, Side-lying, Sitting-short sit, long sit, side sit, ring sit, Quadruped, Kneeling, Half-kneeling, Standing, and Walking. If the child possesses higher level skills, the evaluation should be extended to include the following: Climbing stairs, Navigating ramps or curbs, Unilateral stance, Running , Jumping, Hopping, Galloping, and Skipping . The child who functions from a wheelchair should be evaluated via observation in terms of the following parameters: Alignment and mobility of body, Shifting of weight, Propulsion of wheelchair , Management of wheelchair and its parts, and Transfer to and from wheelchair⁹

5) Assessment OF Postural Control

In assessing postural control of the infant and child with cerebral palsy, it is

important to understand several concepts. Postural activity is noted when the child has muscle activation against the supporting surface. An example would be the infant, at 7 to 9 months of age, who has just learned how to gain stability in sitting by pushing his or her legs into the floor. The arms and hands are now free to explore toys and play, as they are no longer needed for propping. Postural preparations are strategies that the child uses well before a functional movement and increase stability by changing the base of support or increasing muscle activation around joints. These changes are in anticipation of a specific task that has been learned previously. The child received sensory input (feedback) from having completed the task previously and makes the necessary postural adjustments to complete the task in the most efficient, effective way. For example, the infant, sitting on the floor, sees a toy to the side and tries reaching for it. If it is too far outside the base of support, the infant may fall in attempting to grab the toy. On the next try, the infant will make adjustments to the base of support and/or muscle activation in the attempt to grasp the toy without falling over.

Feed forward is identified in postural preparations for movement. It occurs as a result of learning through experience. Postural setting is the muscles getting active around a joint or joints, without obvious movement, in anticipation of the task. Current motor sciences endorse the importance of anticipation (feed forward) in movement and postural control. Feed forward is learned through trial-and-error practice as the example illustrates and must be client generated and be goal or task oriented. Postural control is learned specific to a task and in a variety of environmental conditions. Motor learning occurs when the child is actively involved in the session and advances from using only the feedback responses to feed forward control.

For example, the child experiences the tactile and proprioceptive properties of objects (feedback) when handling and playing with toys. This helps in reshaping of the hand in preparation for more refined reach and grasp tasks in the future.

When assessing the infant/child's postural control, find answers to the following questions:

- Does the child have a variety of ways to transition between postures or only stereotypic choices?
- Does the child actively push into the supporting surface with the pelvis or extremities?
- Is the child able to repeat movements or tasks and make small changes in his or her motor performance? ³

6) Assessment of Postural Tone

In assessing the child's stiffness, it is necessary to describe the relative amounts of stiffness in the head, neck, trunk, and extremities. For example, the child with classic spastic diplegia will typically demonstrate hypotonic through the neck and trunk while having increased stiffness in both legs. Frequently, one can observe stiffness of the limbs

while watching a child play. However, for detailed and accurate information, it is necessary to "feel" the child transition between postures and move the limbs through space. The clinician may feel the change in the level of stiffness while working with and assisting the child to move through space. This response is typical as the child

expends greater effort to perform a task or as the child brings his or her center of mass higher off the support surface. The child may also exhibit an increase in the level of stiffness in particular limbs, frequently in the legs, with an increase in the level of excitement of the activity or the transition.

It is necessary to distinguish between stiffness that is a primary impairment (a loss or abnormality at the organ or organ system level of the body) and stiffness that is compensatory (used by the child to compensate for a primary impairment).

It is important to identify compensatory stiffness. Focusing on the child with spastic diplegia again, the level of stiffness may increase in the upper extremities when the child is seated on a bench secondary to the hypotonic noted in the trunk and the child seeking greater stability as the body is moved higher against gravity. The child may elevate the shoulders and attempt to use the scapulae in adduction with the arms in humeral hyperextension and elbow flexion as an assist to sitting erect because he or she cannot push the hips and thighs into the base of support for stability. The increased stiffness noted in the arms and shoulder girdles is considered compensatory stiffness.

Signs of increased stiffness include distal fixing (toe curling or fisting), difficulty moving a body segment through a range, asymmetric posture, retracted lips and tongue, and so on. Signs of decreased stiffness include excessive collapse of body segments, loss of postural alignment, and inability to sustain a posture against gravity. A child may also have fluctuating levels of stiffness, which is noted as signs of both increased and decreased levels of stiffness. Two more commonly known types of cerebral palsy exhibiting fluctuating levels of stiffness are athetosis and ataxia.⁹

7) Musculoskeletal Assessment

Persistent shortening of a muscle or group of muscles without adequate activation of antagonists—resulting from spasticity, increased or decreased stiffness, weakness, or static positioning—places the child at risk for soft tissue conjunctures and, over time, bony deformity. With an awareness of the sequence usually seen in atypical motor development and with knowledge of the postural and movement consequences, the therapist must be alert for areas at risk for contracture and deformity.

a) Goniometric Measurements

Range of motion (ROM) should be measured with a goniometer at joints with limited motion. Muscles whose influence is exerted across two joints should be examined and elongated over both joints when measurements are taken. Move the child's limb slowly through the full range to avoid eliciting a stretch reflex. The first "catch" or tightening of the muscle is the child's functional range for tasks. Therapists can slowly and carefully stretch muscles beyond this point to the second "catch" or what is called the absolute range. The therapist must work with the child and caregivers to bring the two values closer together, approximating the functional range to the absolute range.

b) Evaluation of the Spine

Mobility of the spine in all planes is necessary for correct alignment; for smooth, symmetric movements of the spine; and for full ROM of the extremities. Evaluation of the child's passive and active movement of the trunk is an essential part of the evaluation. Passive spinal flexion can be evaluated with the child in supine by

rounding the spine and putting the child's knees up to his or her chest. Look for the spinous processes to be showing evenly down the child's spine. This is smooth flexion of the spinal column. If an area is flattened without the spinous processes showing or showing less-it is indicative of a decrease in spinal flexion. Spinal extension, lateral flexion, and rotation are most easily assessed in sitting. The pelvis must be stabilized by the therapist and the trunk taken through the various movements. Note the smoothness of the movement, the end range and end feel, the symmetry in the trunk, and the amount of movement at each joint in the spinal column.

The therapist must document any deviation from normal in the spinal curves. Note scoliosis and excessive hypnosis and lordosis and whether the curves are structural or functional.

c) Examination of the Hip and Pelvis

The child with cerebral palsy, typically with spastic diplegia, commonly has tightness in the hip flexors, adductors, and internal rotators with resultant limitation in hip extension, abduction, and external rotation. The Thomas test is used to identify a flexion contracture of the hip. Abduction and adduction of the hip should be assessed with the hip and knee extended. Internal and external rotation of the hip should be measured while the infant or child is prone with the hips extended and the knees flexed.

Subluxed or dislocated hips can occur in children with very tight hip flexion, adduction, and internal rotation. The subluxed or dislocated hip has limited abduction. The Ortolani click test is used to help determine whether a hip is congenitally dislocated. The infant/child is supine, and both hips are flexed to 90 degrees. The hips are abducted and externally rotated, with the examiner's first two fingers placed over the lateral hip and the infant's knees in the examiner's palms. If the hip is dislocated, the femoral head can slide over the acetabular rim, reducing the hip and producing a palpable and sometimes audible click. An older child in the same position will be evaluated by the apparent length of the femur. A subluxed or dislocated hip is suggested by a relatively shorter femoral length.

d) Femoral Anteversion

Femoral anteversion is a torsion or internal rotation of the femoral shaft on the femoral neck. Other terms that may be synonymous with femoral ante version include fetal femoral torsion and persistent fetal alignment of the hip.

At birth, an infant has approximately 40 degrees of femoral ante version, as measured by the angle between the transcondylar axis of the femur and the femoral axis of the neck.

The neonate also has 25 degrees of flexion contracture of the hip owing to intrauterine positioning and physiologic flexor tone. In the progression of typical development, hip flexors lengthen as the result of gravitational pull while the child is lying in either a prone or supine position. Active extension and external rotation of the

hip tighten the anterior capsule of the hip joint, thus producing a torque or torsional stress that decreases the anteversion that is present from birth. In addition to the effects of the tightened hip capsule, the hip extensors and external rotators insert near the proximal femoral growth plate.

When activated, the extensors and external rotators pull on the plate and help decrease the torsion on the femur. The result of the various forces is that the adult value of 15 degrees of femoral ante version is reached by 16 years of age. Internal and external rotation of the hip are tested with the hip in a position of extension (i.e., with the child in a prone position with knees flexed). Femoral ante version may be suspected when external rotation at the hip is substantially less than internal rotation.

The infant or child with cerebral palsy often has over activity and shortening of the flexors of the hip and poor control of extensors and of external rotators of the hip. Beals, in 1969, studied 40 children with CP and found that the degree of femoral ante version was normal at birth. However, this study also revealed that the amount of ante version did not decrease over the first few years of life, as occurs with typically developing children. After 3 years of age, there was no significant change in ante version with either age or ambulation status. The sample of children with CP had a mean of 14 degrees greater ante version than the children without CP.

Staheli and associates found greater angles of ante version of the femur in the involved lower extremity of a group of children with CP than was found in their uninvolved limb.

e) Examination of the knee

The child with cerebral palsy may have limited knee flexion or extension as a result of inadequate length of the quadriceps or hamstrings. Length of the medial and lateral hamstrings and the rectus femoris, all of which cross two joints, should be assessed elongating the muscle over the knee and the hip. Passive straight leg raising or measurement of the popliteal angle will indicate the degree of hamstring tightness. If hamstring tightness is excessive, the child may be unable to sit on the ischium with 90-degree of flexion of the hip, and stride length may be limited during ambulation.

Tightness of the quadriceps, which limits flexion of the knee, can be identified by looking for a patella that is located more superiorly than typical and by assessing the degree of flexion of the knee with the child in a prone position.

f) Tibial Torsion

The specific angle of torsion is determined by the intersection of a line drawn vertically from the tibial tubercle and a line drawn through the malleoli.

Like the femur, the tibia undergoes developmental torsional changes. The malleoli are parallel in the frontal plane at birth. During infancy and early childhood, the tibia rotates externally, which places the lateral malleolus in a posterior position relative to the medial malleolus.

The "unwinding" of the tibia, or the progression from relative internal to external tibial torsion, is attributable to changes in force on the tibia arising from the decrease in femoral anteversion that occurs as the child grows.

g) Examination of the foot

Dorsiflexion of the ankle is often limited in the child with cerebral palsy and must be assessed with the subtalar joint maintained in a neutral position. Neutral alignment will prevent hypermobility of the forefoot while ensuring excursion of the hindfoot.

Midtarsal movement can be assessed stabilizing the hindfoot with one hand while passively supinating and pronating the forefoot with the other. Toes should be straight and mobile with approximately 90 degrees of extension available at the first metatarsophalangeal joint.

With the child standing, the calcaneus should be vertical or slightly inverted in relation to the lower one-third of the leg. Children should begin to show a longitudinal arch at 3.5 to 4 years of age. Depression of the medial longitudinal arch is caused by adduction and plantar flexion of the talus with relative eversion of the calcaneus. This alignment is also associated with internal rotation of the lower extremity. Another mechanism for malalignment during standing occurs in children who have stiffness into extension, including plantar flexion. Their calcaneus is often maintained in some degree of plantar flexion and does not truly participate in weight bearing. The talus stays plantar flexed with "apparent full weight bearing," with pronation achieved through hypermobility into extension through themidtarsal joint. These two mechanisms must be examined carefully when considering an orthosis for standing or ambulating.

h) Discrepancy in Leg Length

Measurement of leg length should be done in supine with the pelvis level in all planes, the hips in neutral rotation and abduction or adduction, and the knees fully extended. Measurements are taken from the anterosuperior iliac spine to the distal aspect of the medial malleolus.

Correction of a discrepancy in the leg length by using a shoe lift is not advocated by some sources. However, children with cerebral palsy who have asymmetry in tone, muscle activation, posture, and movement are placed at even greater risk for muscle shortening and scoliosis when a discrepancy in leg length exists. Such a child will try to equalize the length by ambulating with the shortened limb in plantar flexion with the heel off the floor, thus maintaining a continually

shortened position of the ankle plantar flexors. Leg length in vertical weight bearing should be equalized as early as possible to facilitate equal growth of the child's long bones. When a full-length shoe lift is used to correct the discrepancy in length, the child should be assessed in a standing posture for symmetry of the posterior iliac spines, anterior superior iliac spines, and the iliac crests. When the child wears an orthosis, the shoe lift thickness must take the thickness of the orthosis into account when determining the necessary thickness of the lift. Shoe lifts can be placed inside the shoe or applied to the shoe sole relatively inexpensively.⁹

8) Evaluation of Gait

A baby prepares for ambulation by acquiring antigravity movement components of the neck, trunk, and extremities while in prone, supine, and side-lying positions.

These movement components are also practiced by the baby in higher level positions against gravity (i.e., sitting, quadruped, kneeling, and standing). Stability of the joints increases as strength is gained in the surrounding musculature. Weight shifting through the body has been practiced by the baby and is mastered in all directions.

From the onset of independent ambulation until approximately 3 years of age, the young child's gait pattern will continue to change with the acquisition of mature components in gait. An early, immature gait pattern is characterized by the following:

- Uneven step length
- Excessive flexion of the hip and knee during swing phase
- Immobility of the pelvis without pelvic tilting or rotation
- Abduction and external rotation of the hips throughout swing phase
- Base of support that is wider than the lateral dimensions of the trunk
- Pronation of the foot as a consequence of the wide base
- Contact with the floor that is made with the foot flat
- Hyperextension of the knee throughout stance phase
- Upper extremities in a high-, medium-, or low-guard position

Sutherland and colleagues described five kinematic gait characteristics that change in typical childhood development during the ages of 1 to 7 years:

1. The duration of single-limb stance increases with age (especially up to the age of 2.5 years).
2. Walking velocity increases steadily (especially up to the age of 3.5 years).
3. Cadence (and its variability) decreases with age.

4. Step length increases (especially until the age of 2.5 years).
5. The ratio of body width to stride width (computed from the "pelvic span," which is measured from the level of the anterosuperior iliac spines, and the "ankle spread," which is the distance between left and right ankle centers during double-limb support) increases rapidly until the age of 2.5 years. It then increases more slowly until the age of 3.5 years, and then plateaus.

To gain the stability not yet available at the trunk and pelvis, an early ambulator maintains a certain degree of scapular adduction, either bilaterally or unilaterally. The high-guard position consists of adduction of the scapulae; extension, abduction, and external rotation of the shoulder; and flexion of the elbow. This position affords the greatest stability by maintaining maximal scapular adduction, leading to strong extension of the trunk with an anterior, immobile pelvis. A medium-guard position reduces the degree of scapular adduction. Shoulder continue to be held in extension, abduction, and external rotation, and elbows are flexed with forearms pronated. The low-guard position consists of scapular adduction with the arms at the sides.

The mature components of gait provide a useful framework for evaluating the gait of a child with cerebral palsy.

1. *Pelvic tilt.* A downward tilt of the pelvis from the horizontal plane occurs on the non-weight-bearing side. This tilt allows the center of gravity to be lowered as the body passes over the stance limb, thus reducing vertical oscillations of the body.
2. *Pelvic rotation.* Transverse rotation of the pelvis in an anterior direction occurs with internal rotation of the lower extremity at the end of the swing phase. This rotation contributes to a narrowing of the base of support and changes the

distribution of weight during stance phase to the lateral border of the foot.

3. *Knee flexion at midstance.* This position permits a more fluid, smoother gait pattern.
4. *Heel strike.* Ankle dorsiflexion near the end of the swing phase readies the foot for contact with the floor made at the heel.
5. *Mature mechanism of the foot and knee.* These mechanisms consist of an extension of the knee just before or at heel strike, flexion of the knee in a midstance position, and extension of the knee at heel-off.
6. *Mature base of support.* The base of support narrows to within the lateral dimensions of the trunk.
7. *Synchronous movement of the upper extremities.* Arm swing achieves a reciprocating movement with the lower extremities. Movements of the upper extremities balance out the leg advance and pelvic rotation that produce angular momentum to the lower body.

9) Gait in Cerebral Palsy

Miller presented typical gait as well as the gait of the child with cerebral palsy and the possible intervention. In 1987, Bleck reviewed 423 patients with cerebral palsy and found 66% to fit in the classification of spastic diplegia. Of those, 79% were independent ambulators, 19% ambulated with external assistance, and 2% were non ambulators. Rosenbaum et al. used the GMFCS to assist clinicians and care givers to look at the infant/child and make predictions based on the findings of the GMFCS. They plotted the patterns of motor development based on longitudinal observations of 657 children with cerebral palsy and felt that the findings will help parents understand the outlook for their child's gross motor function based on age and

the GMFCS level.

Many children with spastic diplegia have limited mobility in their lumbar spine, pelvis, and hip joints and show limited asymmetric pelvic tilt or pelvic rotation during gait. In an effort to compensate for the lack of mobility of the lower body, these children shift their weight and maintain balance by using excessive mobility through the head, neck, upper trunk, and upper extremities. Their hips stay flexed during stance, and full extension of the hip is never achieved. Excessive adduction and internal rotation of the hip are frequently found; in severe cases, the medial aspect of the knees may approximate. Depending on the function of the pelvic, lumbar, and ankle musculature, the knees may be either flexed or hyperextended during stance. The feet may be in valgus outside the lateral dimensions of the trunk, or they may be close together in a narrow base of support in plantar flexion with the heels off of the floor. There can be concern and confusion regarding the differentiation between idiopathic toe walking and spastic diplegic cerebral palsy. Hicks et al found that idiopathic toe walkers typically have heel cord contracture but minimal or no hamstring tightness, along with increased knee extension in stance and increased external rotation of the foot with increased plantar flexion. Conversely, they found that children with cerebral palsy had an essentially normal gait pattern with the exception of sustained knee flexion at terminal stance and initial contact. Although children with more severe involvement may require an assistive device for ambulation, many children ambulate without any devices, or with only a shoe insert or orthosis. Generally, children with spastic diplegic cerebral palsy ambulate at about half the speed of children without cerebral palsy, and the self-selected velocity is usually the most efficient rate of ambulation.⁹

10) Functional examination

a) **Sitting**

Evaluate sitting to decide whether the child needs support.

Children with adequate sitting balance are more functional.

b) **Balance**

Balance and equilibrium reactions are prerequisites for walking. Evaluate balance in all children. Push the standing child gently from the front, back, and side to see whether he or she can promptly regain balance. Assess deficiency of balance and equilibrium using the Romberg sign, unilateral standing balance test and the hop test.

c) **Mobility**

A crucial part of the examination is the observation of the child's walking pattern. Video recordings of the child's movement also guide treatment. Ask the family to obtain photographs or video recordings of their child to understand how the child functions at home. Computerized gait analysis is possible in advanced centers. The non ambulatory child is placed on the floor to assess his mobility. The child may roll, creep, crawl or 'walk on all fours'.

d) **Functional scales**

Different scales are used to assess the functional status of patients with CP. Some are descriptive and compare the child with normal age-matched peers whereas a few of them measure change over time that occurs with growth and treatment. Functional tests identify babies and children who have delayed gross or fine motor development and record the progress of those children under treatment. Quality of life is measured with scales such as the Child Health Questionnaire and the Care and Comfort

Measure. Study, skill and experience render the application and scoring of most of these scales easier. The Gross Motor Function Measure (GMFM) and the Gross Motor Classification System (GMFCS) have been the most helpful to date and they are freely available for use.

i. Gross Motor Function Measure (GMFM)

The GMFM was developed to measure changes in gross motor function over time in children with CP. It compares the child with normal children of the same age. The GMFM is a reliable scale to evaluate gross motor function. It measures the child's skill in lying, rolling, sitting, crawling, kneeling, standing, walking, running, and jumping, but it does not measure the quality of movement. It can be used for children from birth to 5 years of age.

ii. Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS)

The Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS) was developed to create a systematic way to describe the functional abilities and limitations in motor function of children With CP. The emphasis is on sitting and walking. The purpose is to classify a child's present gross motor function. Five levels are used in the GMFCS from very mild to very severe. The levels are based on the functional limitations, the need for assistive technology and wheeled mobility. The quality of movement is not very important. Because motor function depends on age, separate scales are used for different age bands. Classification at 2 years allows one to predict prognosis at age 20 years.

The GMFCS is an important tool for therapists treating children with CP. It is easy to use; classifying a child takes 5 - 15 minutes. Therapists from various disciplines can easily use this scale for their patients. Therefore, it provides a basic

understanding of the level of involvement of a child for all those involved in caring for the child. The use of the GMFCS is becoming increasingly common in CP clinics as a universal tool for communication with colleagues, determining the prognosis and planning treatment.³

Therapeutic Intervention

The Therapeutic team should consist of the infant or child and the family, medical staff, allied health professionals and paraprofessionals, and educational team based on the child's functional abilities and needs (both in the medical model and the school system). The infant/child and family are the core of the team, with the emphasis placed on function in the home as well as in the community (including school, recreation, etc.).³

The therapeutic intervention must be guided by the functional outcomes and/or the participation outcomes that the child and family have identified upon seeking physical therapy intervention. With the outcome(s) identified, the physical therapist must analyze the function or task that is desired and compare the task analysis to the completed assessment of the infant or child. Answers to the following questions should assist the therapist in selecting and sequencing the appropriate treatment strategies to meet the needs of the client and be successful in the function or task:

- What strengths/competencies does the client possess that will provide a foundation upon which to build toward the functional outcome?
- Which posture and movement behaviours interfere with the successful completion of the functional outcome?
- Which identified impairments are critical to the successful completion of the functional outcome?
- How should these impairments be prioritized with regard to the functional

outcome? Place the impairment that most greatly impacts the task first on a list of five or six impairments and continue to place the other four or five impairments in order of importance to the identified outcome.

- What treatment strategies can be utilized to address each of the prioritized impairments?
- Do any of the identified treatment strategies address more than a single impairment? Can they be combined?
- Which of the impairments must be treated in preparation to address any of the other identified impairments?
- In what order must the strategies be sequenced to be most successful?
- How many repetitions are necessary for the client to "own" the task at the end of the treatment session?
- How much assistance is necessary to achieve the desired outcome? Can this be decreased within the treatment session?

Once the session is completed, the therapist should analyze the results of the session and make notes about any necessary changes in treatment strategies, sequencing, amount of assistance or facilitation required, a change in a device used for assistance, or the number of repetitions used within the session. Tieman et al. looked at the capability and performance of mobility in children with cerebral palsy across the settings of home, school, and outdoors/ community that must be taken into account when writing and determining successful completion of the identified functional outcomes. They found that capability and performance of mobility of the children varied across settings. They tended to perform less well in the higher demand settings such as school or the community. Since much of the testing in

physical therapy occurs in the clinical setting, one must be cautious in determining when an outcome is completed successfully and use child and parent or school staff reporting to be accurate.

Documenting and quantifying outcomes for the client is critical to physical therapy. The Gross Motor Function Measure (GMFM) and the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS) have been identified as useful standardized tools to document current status and functional change with intervention provided for children with cerebral palsy.

Children with cerebral palsy face a lifetime of functional challenges that can intermittently be ameliorated with physical therapy. In general, it is to allow the infant or child to become the most independent possible in performing functional tasks throughout his or her lifetime. The provision of physical therapy should change in frequency and duration as the infant or child grows and develops, with periods of time when the child does not receive formal physical therapy intervention. Therefore, it is paramount that we identify the times that are most critical to receive formal therapy, the times when therapy can be supplemented or replaced with adjunctive therapies, and the times when the child, adolescent, or young adult can take a hiatus from formal therapy and continue an independent program for health and wellness with identified points for reassessment by the physical therapist. As an example, physical therapy can minimize the need for or postpone orthopaedic surgery, thereby reducing the number of surgeries a child may need. Prepubescence and puberty are time periods when the adolescent should be in active physical therapy, as the long bones grow faster than the muscles can accommodate. The result is that the child/young adult will potentially develop poor posture, pain, and movement compensations, which will result in a

decrease in his or her current functional abilities. Considering other times when physical therapy is the most beneficial, it is necessary to look at the infant or child in terms of his or her current function, prognosis for acquiring new functional skills, "windows of opportunity" when he or she may make the greatest gains in the shortest period of time, his or her growth spurts, recent surgery, the family's ability to manage a home program at each level of the infant or child's progress, and the infant or child's level of comfort in terms of pain and deformity. A burst of physical therapy is essential after neurosurgery and orthopaedic surgery, after growth spurts that impact the bio-mechanics of the movement, and whenever there is a "window of opportunity." Intensive therapy may be required for shorter periods of time to accomplish specific tasks. According to Fetters, we need a new way to look at treatment, and we need ecologically valid movement goals to guide treatment of motor dysfunction, as well as research in motor control.

Treatment from a dynamic systems approach considers the outcome of treatment to be working on the system when it is in transition. According to this approach, the therapist would complete an assessment, then attempt to predict under what conditions and how clients will change. The therapist would also anticipate system wide responses to small changes in a control parameter. For example, placing an orthotic device in a shoe may alter the pattern of weight bearing, thus influencing the posture of the knee, hip, pelvis, and trunk. "When patients are able to explore and use the limits of postures to actively engage in tasks, they are adaptive and independent.

There is no singular recommended intervention for any specific category of cerebral palsy as each infant and child presents a unique array of functional competencies,

desired outcomes, functional limitations, and impairments. It is common and necessary to use various principles from a variety of treatment approaches for an effective and efficacious treatment. The therapist must determine the array of methods useful for client. Frequently, infants and children will demonstrate impairments that cross two or more types of cerebral palsy.⁹

1) Components of child rehabilitation

Child rehabilitation consists of improving mobility, preventing deformity and educating the parents about the child's problem. It also involves helping the child to learn the skills he will need in daily life, school and while playing with friends. Lastly, rehabilitation means decreasing the complications which arise as a result of the child's neuromuscular impairments.

Therapeutic exercises help the child learn how to sit, stand, and walk. The child also learns how to use his remaining potential to compensate for the movements he cannot perform. Decreasing spasticity, gaining muscle strength and improving joint alignment decrease deformity. The education of caregivers involves gently coaching them to set reasonable expectations for their child, and teaching them to follow their child's exercises at home. Parents should encourage their children to participate in daily living activities by using the functional skills they learned during therapy. Community and social support is another aspect of rehabilitation.

There is no method which can decrease the neurological impairment. Explain to the parents not to spend valuable time and hope with alternative treatments. Aim to have the child fulfill his maximum physical, intellectual and psychological capacity and have a happy childhood as close to normal as possible. Focus on the child's abilities and interests. Try to improve function by working on these. The child can easily improve in the activities he likes doing. This will enable him to have a happy childhood and a job in the future.

The main aim of rehabilitation is providing an education for the child, and to help him grow up to be a productive, independent adult. Various therapy procedures exist some of which do not really relate to real world situations. The skills that the child gains during therapy sessions should be useful within the community. Never ignore the child's education throughout the various therapy procedures. Always aim to send the child to school for an education and prepare him for community integration.

2) **Planning rehabilitation**

The child begins to receive physiotherapy when he is a baby. The toddler uses assistive devices for mobility. Bracing may be necessary as the child begins to walk. Sports and recreation are crucial for the school aged child. Play is important beginning in infancy throughout adolescence. Have short and long term goals depending on the child's expected functional outcome. Evaluate the child, specify these short and long term functional goals and set a time limit in which you expect the child to achieve these goals. Review the plan if the child cannot achieve the expected function in the predetermined time period.

3) **Factors influencing rehabilitation outcome**

Consider the following factors in the rehabilitation plan.

a) **Treatment team**

Together, the rehabilitation team works to assist the person with CP to achieve his place in the society. A productive interaction between the physicians and the therapists is essential for the maximum benefit of the child. All those involved with the child must have a basic understanding on the diagnosis, family expectations, degree of motor dysfunction, functional goals and the therapy program.

b) **Medical problems of the child**

The rehabilitation physician and the team must be prepared to anticipate certain acute and chronic problems during the rehabilitation of the child with CP. Total body and some severely involved diplegics have visual and hearing deficits, mental retardation, cortical sensory deficits and communication deficits that prevent the child from reaching his maximum potential.

c) **The child's character**

The motivation to move, temperament, behavior/cooperation and the willingness to take risks are important determinants of rehabilitation outcome. These personality characteristics of the child are independent of impairment or disability.

d) **The family**

Some families provide their children with ample experiences and opportunities that enrich their environment and increase their ability to achieve new skills. Family resources, quality of home environment, family support and parent/caregiver expectations guide the plans of long-term care for the disabled child.

e) **Physiotherapy**

Physiotherapy helps improve mobility. It is the basic treatment in all children with CP. It consists of exercises, bracing and activities towards reaching specific functional goals. It aims to bring the child to an erect position, give the child independent mobility and prevent deformity. Organize physiotherapy to fit into the family's lifestyle.³

4) **General principles of physiotherapy**

Physiotherapy begins in early infancy and continues throughout adolescence. The primary purpose is to facilitate normal neuromotor development. With the help of correct positioning, appropriate stimulation and intensive exercise the therapist tries to gain head control, postural stability and good mobility in the child. This is possible only to the extent of the child's neurological capacity. Even with vigorous physiotherapy many children remain functionally impaired in varying degrees.

There are different methods of therapy for children with neurological impairments. Even though they differ in the techniques they use, basic principles remain the same. The problems of neuromotor development are difficulty flexing and extending the body against gravity, difficulty sitting and functional ambulation.

For functional ambulation a child needs motivation to move and explore the world around him. He must have enough muscle strength and control. He must be able to shift his body weight and have an awareness of body position in space at rest and during movement. Visual and vestibular systems must be sufficient. There must not be any deformities interfering with joint function.

In physiotherapy sessions the therapist works with the child in supine and prone positions to improve head and trunk control. She supports the child in the sitting position to develop weight shifting and unilateral balance, ability to rotate the body and the ability to respond to sudden changes in position. The rehabilitation team

strives for longterm, functional mobility in a variety of environments so that the child will integrate into the community and social life in a healthy way.³

5) Therapy methods

Stretching, range of motion and strengthening exercises are essential in all children. In addition, neurofacilitation techniques stimulate the central nervous system to establish normal patterns of movement. These neurofacilitation techniques were developed over the years to minimise the neurological impairment and help the healing CNS to reorganize. This has not been possible and the focus of therapy shifted from trying to heal the neurological lesion to increasing motor function. There is no treatment method that can heal the lesion in the CNS. The intact neurons in the brain may substitute for lost function, new synapses may form and reorganisation of neurons take place so that the child gains function as he grows. This process is termed neuronal plasticity. The present neurofacilitation methods stimulate the CNS and accelerate neuromotor maturation through the process of neuronal plasticity. The Vojta method is common in Eastern Europe whereas the neurodevelopmental training technique established by B. Bobath and named after her is widely used in the Western world. Both because of difficulties in diagnosing CP in infancy, and the inherent potential of the CNS to heal, it is extremely difficult to judge the actual success of such procedures.

Plan the exercises according to the mobility needs of the child. It is not enough to have a therapy session only once during the day with the therapist. Children with CP need to exercise at home to gain maximum function. The success of the techniques used in physical therapy depends on repeated practice. The parents must repeat the exercises with their children every day and observe children for improvement or changes that may be needed.³

6) Therapeutic Exercise

Therapeutic exercise plays an important role in the habilitation/rehabilitation of the infant or child with cerebral palsy. The exercise program should be developed in relation to the assessment of the infant/child, the identified long- and short-term functional outcomes, the functional abilities, and the impairment goals of the infant/child. Current research and understanding of motor control and motor learning make it possible, even mandatory, to promote a strengthening program with children of all ages who have cerebral palsy. Strength training has been shown to improve identified parameters of gait and improve muscle performance. According to Damiano, strengthening is justifiable to improve a motor skill or function and can be accomplished when the child has at least some voluntary control in a muscle group. When utilized along with invasive procedures such as dorsal rhizotomy, intrathecal baclofen pump, soft tissue and bony surgeries, and Botox injections, strength training may prolong the outcomes of these procedures and the strengthening may be more effective.

To have an effective strength-training program, the child must:

1. comprehend the process;
2. consistently produce a maximal or near-maximal effort;
3. be motivated and be able to attend to the task; and
4. have a family that can support the program and the child.

A strength-training program can be used with children as young as 4 to 5 years of age who can fulfil the abovementioned requirements. For the therapist to develop a training program, the child must be able to lift a load two to three times before fatigue

in order to strengthen the muscle. To promote strengthening, one must use high loads with a low number of repetitions (three to eight) arranged in multiple sets with a rest between each set. To improve on muscle endurance, the child should lift less of a load but for more repetitions (8 to 20) before resting. With improvement, the therapist can increase the load or the number of repetitions. When strengthening particular muscle groups in children with cerebral palsy, it is imperative that the therapist promote a balance of muscle activity across a joint and not exercise the same muscle or muscle group on consecutive days. Damiano further presents multiple references that show improvement in scores on the GMFM, gait, and self-perception. Centers across the United States have instituted strength-training programs in their clinics with anecdotal results showing improvement in function and participation with peers.

One can achieve a strengthening program without the use of weights by carefully selecting the activities that require the use of specified muscle groups to be successful. This allows the therapist to develop programs for infants and children who are too young to comprehend a strength training program. Careful documentation of the activity or position utilized will allow the therapist to design a strengthening progression by changing the activity or position required. When the infant or child is too weak or has too little postural control or ability to sustain postural control to utilize resistance of weights or even of his or her own body weight as resistance, the therapist can position the infant or child to eliminate gravity or to provide the handling and assistance necessary for the infant or child to complete the motion against gravity.

7) Sensory System

It is necessary to address the infant or child's sensory systems as they specifically affect motor performance and functional activities. The infant or child with cerebral palsy has difficulty receiving and interpreting sensory information accurately, and is therefore at a disadvantage to respond to the information with appropriate motor output. The therapist must provide the infant or child with sensory information and movement experiences that will help to correctly interpret sensory information and then select a motor output that is functional. When the sensory information or "diet" is supplied throughout the infant or child's day, he or she will more quickly and accurately be able to apply the information in a functional way. It is necessary to educate parents and teachers in ways that will assist the infant or child in learning about sensory information and how it relates to his or her body. Some examples include:

- Use firm pressure when towelling dry after the bath.
- Provide a swinging motion to the infant or child every time you pick him or her up.
- "Dance" with the infant or young child on your shoulder or in your arms when passing between rooms.
- Encourage floor play with rolling over, pushing up, moving the extremities, etc.
- Propose play activities requiring use and strength of the hands such as play dough, silly putty, playing in wet sand, etc.
- Provide opportunities for "heavy" work such as pushing a laundry basket of clothes or books, pushing the grocery cart or carrying selected "heavier" groceries into the house or pantry, pushing the chair under the classroom table, replacing the toys that are heavier during classroom clean-up time, etc.
- Select equipment on the playground that provides movement to the child such as

sliding boards, see-saws, merry-go-rounds, jungle gyms, etc., according to his or her capabilities and available safety features.

8) Secondary Musculoskeletal Changes

A child's difficulty in performing functional tasks may be attributable to changes within the musculoskeletal system. An assessment should identify which muscles are shortened, which soft tissue is shortened, and where the fascia has thickened over time owing to injury or stress of movement. These areas should be addressed so that smoothly coordinated motor tasks can be accomplished.

Other Consideration

The therapist should avoid prolonged holding in static positions during treatment. Smoothly graded transitions in movement with brief holding of midline or neutral alignment are more desirable than extended periods in static postures. Facilitated weight shifts and transitional movements should be varied, both in speed and range, so the infant or child cannot anticipate rhythmic displacements. Initiation of weight shifts and transitions in movement are important parts of treatment with the therapist continually looking to increase the variability of the postures and movements and the choices that the infant or child can make in order to achieve fluid, independent movement. It is imperative that the infant or child use active movement as much as possible, supported and/or assisted by the therapist, and that opportunities are provided for repetition of a task or *skill* in order for the infant or child to learn it.

provide examples of activities for treatment sequences within treatment sessions. These are to be used as guides only-not prescribed activities for a particular

infant or child with cerebral palsy. There may be different responses noted with a given activity.⁹

9) Neurofacilitation techniques

Sensory input to the CNS produces reflex motor output. The various neurofacilitation techniques are based on this basic principle. All of the techniques aim to normalize muscle tone, to establish advanced postural reactions and to facilitate normal movement patterns.

f) *Vojta method of therapy*

Vojta established 18 points in the body for stimulation and used the positions of reflex crawling and reflex rolling. He proposed that placing the child in these positions

and stimulation of the key points in the body would enhance CNS development. In this way the child is presumed to learn normal movement patterns in place of abnormal motion. Positioning and stimulation techniques are different from NDT. Vojta states that therapy should be applied by the primary caregiver at home at least 4-5 times daily and stopped after a year if there is no improvement.³

g) *Bobath neurodevelopmental therapy*

This is the most commonly used therapy method in CP worldwide. It aims to normalize muscle tone, inhibit abnormal primitive reflexes and stimulate normal movement. It uses the

idea of reflex inhibitory positions to decrease spasticity and stimulation of key points of control to promote the development of advanced postural reactions. It is believed that through positioning and stimulation, a sense of normal movement will develop. An important part of therapy of the infant is teaching the mother how to position the child at home during feeding and other activities. The baby is held in the antispastic position to prevent contracture formation.^{3,9}

Benefits and limitations

Physiotherapy cannot correct the movement problem in CP. A few rare cases reach their full potential through physiotherapy alone, the majority of children need other interventions. The

effect of physiotherapy in preventing contractures and deformities or improving balance and coordination is also limited. Physiotherapy is beneficial in promoting the neurological development of the child and teaching the child to use his existing potential in the best possible way. By improving mobility, physiotherapy may also prevent secondary mental and psychosocial retardation. However, the success of treatment depends on the neurological capacity of the child. An allegory can be made with sports: even with the best coaching, an athlete cannot compete in the Olympics if he does not have the potential. Similarly, even with the best physiotherapy, the child with CP cannot walk if he does not have the neurological capacity. The treatment team must be careful therefore not to raise any false hopes about the outcome of physiotherapy in children.

The efficacy of neurofacilitation techniques in improving the neurological impairment is controversial. Meta-analyses of neurodevelopmental therapy (Bobath)

have shown that the functional status of the children at school age are the same regardless of having received therapy or not.

Long hours of intensive physiotherapy can harm the child in many ways. It interferes with play, schooling, family and peer relations. Organize therapy so as not to disturb normal childhood.³

10) Sensory Integration

Sensory integration (SI) focuses on sensory aspects and their impact on motivation, attention, movement, and socioemotional well-being. "Sensory Integration (SI) is the primary treatment approach with children who have learning disorders, attention deficits, and autism." The principles of SI treatment include:

1. Providing the opportunity to experience a variety of controlled sensory input to encourage the production of an adaptive response that includes motor behaviors, social interactions, or cognitive skills
2. Encouraging the child to utilize intrinsic motivation
3. Promoting purposeful behaviors within a meaningful activity.

11) Electrical Stimulation

Interest in using electrical stimulation in the population with cerebral palsy has been growing over time. Damiano mentioned its use as a possibility with children who are unable to comprehend or follow a muscle-strengthening program or who are too weak to do strengthening of the muscles in isolation. The two methods that have been researched and most extensively used are neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) and threshold electrical stimulation (TES). NMES is the application of

stimulation of an electrical current of sufficient intensity to elicit muscle contraction resulting in greater muscle strength. When this is used in a task-specific manner in which a muscle is stimulated when it should be contracting during a functional activity, it is referred to as functional electrical stimulation (FES). Daichman et al. found that NMES was effective in strengthening the quadriceps of a 13-year-old adolescent with spastic diplegic cerebral palsy for the development of new skills such as stair climbing. Research that has been completed on this method was compiled and reviewed in the article by Kerr et al. stating that the scarcity of well-controlled trials makes it difficult to support definitively or discard the use of electrical stimulation in the pediatric population with cerebral palsy. There appears to be more evidence to support the use of NMES than TES, but the findings must be interpreted with caution due to the lack of insufficient statistical power to provide conclusive evidence for or against these modalities. "The age and type of patient most likely to benefit from this intervention and optimal treatment parameters are as yet unknown." ⁹

12) Biofeedback

In CP, EMG biofeedback has had little application, with no major controlled studies. Nash et al. applied biofeedback treatment to control spasticity for three children with spastic diplegia at risk for contractures. They reported that after a 10-week training period, spasticity in the gastrocnemius muscle decreased significantly. Toner et al. studied the effect of biofeedback training on ankle joint function in children with CP and reported significant increases in active range of motion (ROM) and dorsiflexor strength, suggesting that biofeedback treatment can improve ankle function. O'Dwyer et al. applied feedback to 15 CP patients aged 6 – 19 years to reduce spasticity and contracture of the triceps surae muscle. Although they found a

significant effect in reducing spasticity, no changes were observed in the degree of muscle contracture. The authors commented that reduction of spasticity has no clinical value and the most effective strategy for reversing muscle contracture might be the utilization of procedures that lengthen the muscles combined with biofeedback training to maintain the achieved muscle length.

Dursun et al. applied EMG biofeedback to Thirty-six children with spastic cerebral palsy and dynamic equinus deformity were included in the study. The biofeedback group consisted of 21 children who each received EMG biofeedback training plus conventional exercise programme. The control group consisted of 15 children who each received conventional exercise programme only. Active range of motion of the ankle joints, muscle tone of plantar flexors, and gait function of the children were evaluated and compared. The study showed that The biofeedback group displayed statistically significant improvements regarding tonus of plantar flexor muscles and active ROM of ankle joints.

Gait function showed statistically significant progress in both of the groups, but the biofeedback group was superior to controls.¹⁷

Adaptive Equipment

Adaptive equipment is often a necessary and useful adjunct to treatment of the infant or child with cerebral palsy. Equipment may be provided to offer postural support to the infant or child, or it may aid functional skills and mobility. Any equipment used should be "family friendly" (functional for family), comfortable, safe, easy to use, and attractive. Adaptive equipment and its use should coincide with and reinforce functional outcomes for the child. The equipment should be reassessed frequently and adapted as necessary based on the infant or child's current requirements and growth.⁹

Lower Extremity Orthoses

ORTHOSIS (plural orthoses) is an external support for a weakened part of the body. Calliper, splints, braces are all different kinds of orthoses. The use of an orthosis is to prevent or correct deformity; keep the limb in a stretched position after therapy or surgery; provide a base of support; enable learning of motor skills especially standing, walking; and to improve walking or gait.¹

Most diplegic children need variations of the ankle foot orthoses (AFO). AFOs provide a stable base for standing and maintain good joint alignment during walking. Prescribe solid, hinged AFOs or ground reaction ankle foot orthoses (GRAFOs) depending on the gait pathology. Resting and night knee ankle foot orthoses (KAFOs) are used to prevent knee and ankle contractures. The child with severe spasticity cannot tolerate these, wakes up often and cries a lot. Do not use night splints if there is severe spasticity or contracture, relieve spasticity first.³

1) Hinged AFOs:

The orthosis has a hinge that allows a limited amount of motion. (i.e., A hinged AFO allows limited up and down motion of the ankle) ¹⁸. some children have mostly foot shaping needs. Hinges are fine, in that case. However, some have control only so far and not with every step. Rather than allow any degree of free forward movement, a back strap is used which lets the brace go so far and no further. This is a "control arc" concept. Allow some range which has demonstrated control (strength equal to the task and reaction speed), but no more. Range without control is, well, you know. ¹⁹

2) Solid AFOs:

Designed to hold the joint in a fixed position (i.e., a solid ankle AFO does not allow motion at the ankle joint.) ¹⁸. Well shaped to the foot, flexible fit with full contact padding at key pressure points. Ball of foot toe-plate area is flexible and not bounded by sides that would impede to roll over. The vertical 10 degree forward pitch is perfect, especially for sneaker wearing. There is sufficient strapping and forward ankle envelopment to keep the foot shaped and positioned where intended. There are two main objectives.

- 1) Walking and
- 2) Shaping the foot against deformity

If the latter is important, then the enveloping fit is ideal. The main problem with this orthosis is that there are certain kids with postures that simply cannot attain this ideal configuration. They need totally custom fit orthoses that, by application of filler material (applied outside the brace), the brace attains an outer contour that looks like

this even though the ankle and foot, inside, do not. Thus we satisfy an inner anatomy shaping-holding need as well as the outer walking geometry. We marry the concepts of orthosis making with prosthesis making.¹⁹

3) Posterior leaf spring AFO

A PLSO is a rigid AFO trimmed aggressively poster laterally and poster medially at the supramalleolar area. This provides flexibility at the ankle and allows passive ankle dorsiflexion during the stance phase. A PLSO provides smoother knee-ankle motion during walking while preventing excessive ankle dorsiflexion, particularly in larger children who have the strength to deform the material. However it also increases knee flexion in stance. Varus-valgus control is also poor because it is repeatedly deformed during weight bearing. The brace breaks when it is repeatedly deformed. These AFOs are frequently renewed because of material failure. A PLSO is an ideal choice in mild spastic equinus. Do not use in patients who have crouch gait and pes valgus.³

4) Anti-recurvatum AFO

This special AFO is molded in slight dorsiflexion or has the heel built up slightly to push the tibia forward to prevent hyperextension during stance phase. Consider prescribing this AFO for the treatment of genu recurvatum in hemiplegic or diplegic children. Anti-recurvatum AFOs may be solid or hinged depending on the child's tolerance.³

5) Ground Reaction foot ankle orthosis:

This custom-made orthosis acts on the ankle and knee joint. The GRAFO utilizes

ground reaction forces to create positive knee extension or knee flexion moments. The ground reaction force is manipulated by setting the ankle plantar flexion/dorsiflexion angle. The anterior tibial pad helps to apply these forces. The force manipulation and application is demonstrated in the figures.²⁰

GRFAO indication:

1. Quadriceps weakness resulting in knee
2. Knee hyperextension in stance.

GRFAO Benefits:

1. Provides independent ambulation whilst preventing knee flexion/hyperextension in stance.
2. Control medio-lateral ankle instability.
3. When articulated a normalized gait is achieved due to the plantarflexion or dorsiflexion range
4. That is permitted.
5. Light-weight and durable.
6. Cosmetic due to intimate fit and clear plastic.
7. Able to be worn inside a shoe.
8. Customization ensures a comfortable fit and that the client therapy goals are met.
9. Ongoing maintenance of fit and straps by the Orthotics Department.²⁰

6) SMO (Supra-Malleolar Orthosis):

SMO is the acronym for Supra-Malleolar Orthosis. The SMO, as with other orthoses, gets its name for the part of the body for which it encompasses. This orthosis supports the leg just above the anklebones or malleoli. The SMO is considered the shortest of the Ankle Foot Orthoses or AFO's.

The SMO is prescribed for patients who have soft, flexible, flat feet. SMO's are often worn by children. The medical term for a flat foot is a pronated foot or pes planus, pes plano-valgus and hyper-pronated foot.

The SMO is designed to maintain a vertical or neutral heel while also supporting the three arches of the foot. This can help improve standing balance and walking. ²¹

7) Foot orthoses (FO)

Foot orthotics does not prevent deformity. They provide a better contact of the sole of the foot with the ground. ³

8) Hip abduction orthoses

Consider using hip abduction orthoses in children with hip adductor tightness to protect hip range of motion and prevent the development of subluxation. It is easier and cheaper to use a simple abduction pillow. Use mainly at night or during periods of rest. There is no scientific evidence to support the belief that they prevent subluxation. One clear indication for hip abduction orthoses is the early period after adductor lengthening. ³

Mobility Aids & Assistive Devices

A child with CP needs to move around, to explore his surroundings and to interact with his peers so that his mental, social and psychological skills develop to the fullest. A variety of mobility aids and wheelchairs provide differing degrees of mobility to these children. Transfer aids such as lift systems assist the caregiver when performing transfers. Passive standing devices called standers allow the child to get accustomed to standing erect and provide therapeutic standing. Some ambulatory children have to use gait aids as well as braces for efficient and safe ambulation. These gait aids are walkers, crutches and canes. They are mainly used to assist with balance, not for weight bearing.

Gait aids help develop balance. The child receives sensory information regarding the position of the body and space by holding onto the walker, crutch or cane. Gait aids decrease energy expenditure, decrease the loads on the joints, improve posture and pain in addition to improving balance.

Gait aids

1) Walkers

All children's walkers should be built from ultralight durable aluminium and supplied with wheels to minimize energy expenditure. Swivel wheels, forearm attachments, hip guides, hand brakes, baskets and seats are added to the walkers if necessary. Walkers provide the greatest support during gait but they pose certain difficulties during stair climbing, among crowds and within narrow corridors.

There are two types of walkers for pediatric use. The anterior open (reverse) walker is also called a postural control walker. Use the reverse

wheeled walker in the majority of children. It provides the best gait pattern and is less energy consuming. Standard forward walkers lead to increased weight bearing on the walker and increased hip flexion during gait. Choose them only in cases where extensor spasticity predominates.

2) Canes, crutches and gait poles

Walking aids are usually prescribed for balance problems. Slowly push the standing child from the side and then from the front and back. Watch for signs of disturbed balance. Canes or gait poles are necessary if the child does not have sufficient lateral balance. Quadruped canes are the next usual step as the balance improves following walker use. Instruct the child to use the quadruped canes lateral to the body rather than out in front. Try to switch from posterior

walker to forearm crutches in adolescents. Gait poles or sticks provide sensory input for gait and facilitate a normal gait pattern, but sometimes are not cosmetically acceptable to patients. Avoid forearm crutches, as children tend to lean forward into these and develop hip flexion contracture. Forearm crutches also lead to the child to bear the body weight on the upper extremities, leading to a pattern of walking on all fours. Use forearm crutches only in children who need an assistive device for weight bearing as well as balance.³

Conclusion:

Various forms of therapy can help a person with the CP diplegic disorder to function and live more effectively. The Physical therapy (PT) programs are designed to encourage the patient to build a strength base for improved gait and volitional movement, together with stretching programs to limit contractures. Many experts believe that life-long physical therapy is crucial to maintain muscle tone, bone structure, and prevent dislocation of the joints. So selecting the most and the effective treatment was our purpose in our study.

In conclusion, there are no set techniques or invariable techniques and times when the therapist must always do it in the common or traditional way. The only must is that the technique must achieve its intention both while it is being performed and after it has been performed. Every patient has different symptoms, signs; indication, surgeries, measurement, and needs even the age are different so every patient needs different treatment and observation than the other.

There is no set of treatment or techniques are effective or must do it only the prevention and the precaution that the therapist must take it in his consideration such as: positioning and stretching so that no deformity will happen.

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Appendix

Summary: Lower-Extremity Joint and muscle Activity

Stance phase:

Tables and figures present a summary of joint and muscle activity for one lower extremity during the stance phase of gait. The tables include the joint position in degrees, resultant GRFV, the moment, type of muscle action, and muscle activity (as determined by EMG). It should realize that although joint positions and muscle actions as supposed to present the average of a normal population, these averages are affected by the speed of gait and may vary among different by the speed of gait and may vary among different investigators. It found considerable variation among individuals in hip flexion-extension, which ranged from a minimum of 20 degree to a maximum of 42 degree. It found that hip joint ROM for women varied from 41 degree at slow walking speed to 52.5 degree. The hip joint ROM for men varied from 44 degree at slow walking speed to 53.6 degree for men at a fast gait speed.

Swing Phase:

Tables and figures present a summary of joint and muscle activity during the swing phase. In the swing phase of gait the primary functions of the swing extremity muscles are to maintain a certain joint position, to accelerate or decelerate the swinging extremity, to ensure toe/foot clearance, and to ensure that the foot is positioned for heel strike.²²

Table 14-2. Summary of Transverse Rotations at Pelvis, Femur, and Tibia (Right Lower Extremity)*

	Initial Contact	Loading Response	Midstance	Terminal Stance	Preswing
Percent of stance gait cycle	0%	12%	31%	50%	62%
Pelvis	Left side begins to move forward	Left side moving forward	Neutral	Left side moving forward	Left side moving forward
Femur	Medial rotation	Medial rotation	Lateral rotation	Lateral rotation	Lateral rotation
Tibia	Medial rotation	Medial rotation	Lateral rotation	Lateral rotation	Lateral rotation
	Initial Swing	Midswing	Terminal Swing		
Percent of swing gait cycle	75%	82%	100%		
Pelvis	Right side moving forward	Neutral	Right side moving forward		
Femur	Medial rotation	Medial rotation	Medial rotation		
Tibia	Medial rotation	Medial rotation	Medial rotation		

*The femur and tibia medially rotate to about 10–20% of stance and then begin laterally rotating to the end of preswing. At initial swing the femur and tibia begin medially rotating again. The degree of transverse rotation that occurs during gait as well as the point in the gait where the rotation occurs varies according to the gait speed. Individual variations also are common.

Table 14-3. Sagittal Plane Analysis (Fig. 14-31)

Heel Strike (Initial Contact) to Foot Flat (End of the Loading Response)					
Joint	Motion	Ground Reaction Force	Moment	Muscle	Contraction
Hip	Flexion: 30–25°	Anterior	Flexion	Gluteus maximus Hamstrings Adductor magnus Quadriceps	Isometric to eccentric
Knee	Flexion: 0–15°	Anterior to posterior	Extension to flexion		Concentric to eccentric
Ankle	Plantarflexion: 0–15°	Posterior	Plantarflexion	Tibialis anterior Extensor digitorum longus Extensor hallucis longus	Eccentric to lower foot to the supporting surface and to control ankle plantarflexion
Frontal Plane Analysis*					
Joint	Motion	Muscle Activity			
Pelvis	Forwardly rotated position on right side of pelvis at initial contact	Gracilis, vastus medialis, semitendinosus Long head of biceps femoris to control medial rotation of tibia Eccentric contraction of tibialis posterior to control valgus thrust on foot.			
Hip	Left side of pelvis begins to move forward				
Knee	Medial rotation of the femur on the pelvis Valgus thrust with increasing valgus Medial rotation of the tibia				
Ankle	Valgus thrust with increasing pronation Subtalar joint pronation reaches a maximum at the end of loading response Transverse tarsal pronation				
Thorax	Right side of thorax is in posterior position at initial contact and begins moving forward				
Shoulder	Right shoulder is slightly behind right hip and moving forward				

*Reference limb is the right lower extremity.

Table 14-4. Sagittal Plane Analysis (Fig. 14-32)*

Foot Flat (End of Loading Response) to Midstance (End of Midstance)					
Joint	Motion	Ground Reaction Force	Moment	Muscle	Contraction
Hip	Extension: 25–0° 20° flexion-0°	Anterior to posterior	Flexion to extension	Gluteus maximus	Concentric to no activity
Knee	Extension: 15–5° 15–5° flexion	Posterior to anterior	Flexion to extension	Quadriceps	Concentric to no activity
Ankle	15° of plantarflexion to 5–10° of dorsiflexion	Posterior to anterior	Plantarflexion to dorsiflexion	Soleus Gastrocnemius Plantarflexors	Eccentric
Frontal Plane Analysis					
Joint	Motion	Muscle Activity			
Pelvis	Right side rotating backward to reach neutral at midstance. Lateral tilting toward the swinging extremity	Hip abductors are active to prevent excessive lateral tilting (gluteus medius tensor fascia lata)			
Hip	Medial rotation of the femur on the pelvis continues to a neutral position at midstance. Adduction moment continues throughout single support	Minimal or no activity			
Knee	There is a reduction in valgus thrust and the tibia begins to rotate laterally	Minimal or no activity			
Ankle-foot	The foot begins to move in the direction of supination from its pronated position at the end of loading response. The foot reaches a neutral position at midstance	The tibialis posterior helps to produce supination			
Thorax	Right side moving forward to neutral				
Thorax	Translating right to neutral				
Shoulder	Moving forward				

*In the period described above, the hip is extending from about 30° of flexion to about 5° of flexion. The GRFV shifts from anterior to posterior and the moment acting around the hip changes from a flexion to an extension moment. The hip extensors cease their activity at or around midstance because the moment is in the desired direction and momentum appears to be sufficient to carry the body forward. Muscle activity at the hip at midstance is mostly abductor activity to stabilize the pelvis. The quadriceps also ceases its activity as the femur advances over the tibia.

Table 14-5. Sagittal Plane Analysis (Fig. 14-33)*

<i>Midstance (Middle of Midstance) to Heel Off (Prior to End of Terminal Stance)</i>					
Joint	Motion	Ground Reaction Force	Moment	Muscle	Contraction
Hip	Extension: 0° of flexion to 10–20° of hyperextension	Posterior	Extension	Hip flexors	Eccentric
Knee	Extension: 5° of flexion to 0°	Posterior to anterior	Flexion to extension	No activity	
Ankle	Plantarflexion: 5° dorsiflexion to 0°	Anterior	Dorsiflexion	Soleus plantarflexors	Eccentric to concentric
Toes (MTP)	Extension: 0–30° of hyperextension			Flexor hallucis longus and brevis Abductor hallucis Abductor digiti quinti Interossei Lumbricals	

<i>Frontal Plane Analysis</i>		
Joint	Motion	Muscle Activity
Pelvis	Right side moving posteriorly from neutral position	Minimal or no muscle activity
Hip	Lateral rotation of femur and adduction	Inconsistent hip adductor activity
Knee	Lateral rotation of tibia	No activity
Ankle-foot	Supination of subtalar joint increases	Concentric plantarflexor activity
Thorax	Right side moving forward	
Shoulder	Right shoulder moving forward	

*A small extension moment exists at the hip and knee and no muscle activity is required at the knee to maintain the knee in extension. The momentum of HAT appears to assist in keeping the knee extended. The dorsiflexion moment at the ankle reaches a peak toward the end of this period and the plantar flexors are active to control the tibia and to raise the heel. Toe extension occurs as a result of a closed-chain response to heel rise.

Table 14-6. Sagittal Plane Analysis (Fig. 14-34)*

Heel Off (End of Terminal Stance) to Toe Off (End of Preswing)					
Joint	Motion	Gravity Line	Moment	Muscle	Contraction
Hip	Flexion: 20° of hypertension to 0°	Posterior	Extension to neutral	Iliopsoas Adductor magnus Adductor longus	Concentric
Knee	Flexion: 0–30° of flexion	Posterior	Flexion	Quadriceps	Eccentric to no activity
Ankle	Plantarflexion: 0–20° of plantarflexion	Anterior	Dorsiflexion	Gastrocnemius Soleus Peroneus brevis Peroneus longus Flexor hallucis longus	Concentric to no activity
Toes (MTP)	Extension: 50–60° of hyperextension			Abductor hallucis Abductor digit quinti Flexor digitorum brevis Flexor hallucis brevis Interossei Lumbricals	Closed-chain response to increasing plantarflexion at the ankle.

Frontal Plane Analysis

Joint	Motion	Muscle Activity
Pelvis	Left side moving forward until left heel contact (right toe off). Lateral tilting to the swing side ceases as the contralateral extremity enters its stance phase and the period of double support begins.	The hip adductors control eccentrically
Hip	Abduction occurs as the weight is shifted onto the opposite extremity. Lateral rotation of femur	
Knee	Inconsistent Lateral rotation tibia	
Foot/Ankle	The weight is shifted to the toes and at toe off only the first toe is in contact with the supporting surface. Supination of subtalar joint	Plantarflexors
Thorax	Translation to the left	
Shoulder	Moving forward	

*Activity in the gastrocnemius and the soleus ceases after the heel leaves the ground. The other plantarflexors cease activity in the order in which they are listed in the sagittal analysis above.

Table 14-7. Sagittal Plane Analysis (Fig. 14-35)*

Acceleration (Initial Swing Through Midswing)			
Joint	Motion	Muscle	Contraction
Hip	Flexion: 0–20° of flexion to 30° of flexion	Iliopsoas Gracilis Sartorius	Concentric
Knee	Flexion: 30° of flexion to 60° of flexion Extension: 60° of flexion to 30° flexion	Biceps femoris Sartorius Gracilis	Concentric
Ankle	Dorsiflexion: 20° plantarflexion to neutral	Tibialis anterior Extensor digitorum longus Extensor hallucis longus	Concentric
Frontal Plane Analysis			
Joint	Motion	Muscle	Contraction
Pelvis	Lateral pelvic tilt to the right (right side drops). Right side moving forward	Left gluteus medius	
Hip	Rotation from lateral to medial rotation		
Knee	From lateral to medial rotation		
Foot-ankle	Unweighted subtalar joint returns to slight supination		
Thorax	Right side moving posteriorly		
Shoulder	Right side moving posteriorly		

*Concentric contractions of the hip flexors occur to ensure adequate hip flexion to bring the extremity forward and accomplish foot clearance. The femur and tibia attain the greatest amount of lateral rotation at the beginning of initial swing and then begin to rotate medially.

Table 14–8. Sagittal Plane Analysis (Fig. 14–36)*

<i>Midswing Through Deceleration (Terminal Swing)</i>			
Joint	Motion	Muscle	Contraction
Hip	Hip remains at 30° flexion	Gluteus maximus	Eccentric
Knee	Extension: 30° flexion to 0°	Quadriceps Hamstrings	Concentric Eccentric
Ankle	Ankle remains in neutral	Tibialis anterior Extensor digitorum longus Extensor hallucis longus	Isometric Isometric isometric

<i>Frontal Plane Analysis</i>		
Joint	Motion	Muscle Activity
Pelvis	Right side moving anteriorly	Right gluteus medius
Hip	Lateral tilting to the left medial rotation	
Knee	Medial rotation	
Ankle		
Thorax	Right side moving posteriorly	
Shoulder	Right shoulder moving posteriorly	

*The hip remains in a position of 30° flexion while the pelvis rotates forward to increase step length. The momentum of the swinging extremity is restrained by eccentric contraction of the hamstrings while full knee extension is ensured by a brief concentric contraction of the quadriceps. The ankle is maintained in a neutral position to ensure ground clearance and readiness for initial contact. The medial rotation of the thigh and tibia continue through terminal swing into the first part of the stance phase.

FIGURE 14–36. The period of gait from midswing (midswing) through terminal deceleration (terminal swing).

FIGURE 14-27. A center of pressure (COP) pathway is shown by the position of the black dot at heel strike (a), at foot flat (b), at the end of midstance (c), and at toe off (d). The COP path may vary among subjects and may be altered by different footwear.

FIGURE 14-31. The period of gait from heel strike (initial contact) to foot flat (end of loading response). The ground reaction force vectors (GRFV) are indicated by the straight arrows. The curved clockwise arrows indicate flexion moments, and the curved counterclockwise arrows indicate extension moments. Notice that the GRFV changes from a position anterior to the axis of the knee at heel strike to posterior to the axis of the knee at foot flat.

FIGURE 14-32. The period of gait from foot flat (end of loading response) to midstance (end of midstance).

FIGURE 14-33. The period of gait from midstance (end of midstance) to heel off (before end of terminal stance).

FIGURE 14-41. Walking gait cycle.